

Career Decision Making of Secondary School Students - A Critical Review

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Abstract:- The world is undergoing rapid changes with scientific technological advances. The need for a skilled workforce with multidisciplinary abilities across the field of sciences, social sciences, and humanities will be increasingly in greater demand. To understand and acquaint with the quickly changing employment landscape and global ecosystem, children should not only learn but also learn how to learn. In this context NEP 2020 has emphasized on the exploration of students' critical thinking, creativity, innovativeness, inquiry-driven attitude, rational thinking, ability to solve problems etc through the overall teaching learning process from foundation to secondary stage which ultimately make a learner confident enough to choose his/her career what he/she desires to pursue. During adolescence, the career choice in further education is one of the most vital decisions that an adolescent has to decide. Thus it is necessary to analyse the present status, factors affecting career decision making of higher secondary students, researchers' suggestions for inculcation of career decision making efficacy among higher secondary students. More than 50 qualitative evidence-based studies were included in this meta-analysis. Lack of self-understanding, lack of relevant information regarding college majors and future employment prospects etc are the issues currently higher secondary students facing, role models of environment, parental support, teacher support, and peer support influence secondary students' career decision, Experience of success, verbal persuasion and psychological condition, low literacy level and lack of career information, self-efficacy, achievement motivation are the trending factors affecting the career decision making of adolescent learners and efficient arrangements of guidance and counselling programs, seminars, workshops, lectures from guest speakers for adolescents career opportunities and career decision making by school administrators and teachers and provide collaborative support and training on career guidance to parents by Professional school counsellors are the best ever suggestions given by many researcher.

Keywords:- Career Decision Making (CDM), Higher Secondary Students.

I. INTRODUCTION

Development of democratic citizenship and improvement of vocational efficiency clearly indicates to empower every individual for earning basic requirements from their early ages rightly stated by Secondary Education Commission. The employment and efficacy depend upon what and how a person chooses his/her career. In this context, several studies suggest students to decide their career in priority basis rather than focusing on employment. Career defines the overall progress and action taken by an individual related to his/her occupation throughout a life time. It is not just referring to one's position, it often includes the jobs held, titles earned and work accomplished over a longer period of time. Career shows the professional progression chosen by a person or during that person's working life. The sum total of life experiences including paid and unpaid work, community, volunteer and family activities defines the term 'Career'. How individuals make decisions to lead their career choices that is examined by a process-oriented model otherwise known as career decision making. During adolescence, the career choice in further education is one of the most vital decisions that an adolescent has to decide. It is quite tough even after they graduate from high school and become indecisive. The large number of mistakes, errors and inaccuracies in choosing a study program in Higher Education that is often faced by high school students is a problem related to career decision making (Qudsyi,2020). The foundation stone for future career trajectory is laid in the high school period where young adults keep their first step towards career related decision making (Gati & Saka, 2001; Gottfredson, 1981; Super, 1990).

To analyse the present status, affecting factors of higher secondary students in context of their career decision making, researchers' suggestions for inculcation of career decision making efficacy the researcher has critically reviewed the related studies from this field conducted in India and abroad.

II. METHODOLOGY

The study has followed a systematic review of more than 50 qualitative evidence-based studies which includes dissertations, theses and published articles. The studies were retrieved from EBSCOHOST, Elsevier, JSTOR, Google scholar, ERIC, SAGE full text collection with help of university library open sources. Researcher has critically analysed and investigated all the literatures to get the answers of the following questions;

- A. *What is the status of career decision making in higher secondary level?*
- B. *What are the factors influencing the career decision making?*
- C. *How the career decision making efficacy can be cultivated?*

A. *What is the status of career decision making in higher secondary level?*

Secondary education is the connecting link between primary and higher education where a student has to decide what profession he wants to pursue or what profession should be the best choice for him. In this context several researchers from abroad and India have given their extreme support towards the inculcation of career decision making self-efficacy among students. Career development is a life-long journey that starts at mid adolescence and ends at retirement (Bozgeyikli & Hamurcu, 2009; Patton, 2009). According to the developmental theory of Super (1957), 15-24 age is considered as the exploration phase of individual career development where the student is categorized by formatting the self-concept and occupational concepts. For adolescents, the decision-making skill is central in career choice making (Scott et al., 1995) But, it becomes a very difficult task for high school students in choosing a suitable study program in higher education and they make unusual mistakes, errors which is an issue related to their career decision making (Prameswari, 2013; Zhou & Santos, 2007; Gati & Saka 2001; Kinanee, 2009; Gati & Saka, 2001; January, 2003; Laskin & Palmo, 1983; Salami & Aremu, 2007). Gati, Krausz & Osipow (1996) revealed in their study that the self-realization, reinvention, new goals creation etc of secondary students should be there with the progress in the career decision making process. Fredman (1991) as cited by Gati & Saka (2001) conducted study on 9th and 10th graders Israeli students' decision-making behaviour where 43% were suffering from studies and job-related problems. In addition to this, feeling dilemma often arises in the minds of senior high school students due to lack of self-understanding, lack of relevant information regarding college majors and future employment prospects (Qudsi et al., 2018). The globalized work force, modern society, burgeoning technological practices, job restructuring have increased pressure for individuals to be more adaptable and flexible (Greenhaus, Callanan, & Godshalk, 2009 ; Kulcsar, Dobrean & Gati, 2020). South Africa had faced 45% student drop-out only due to wrong course choice of the students and inability to cope with the demands of curriculum which fastened the relationship exploration studies between career decision

making and the identity development of high school learners (Woollacott 2003).

B. *What are the factors influencing the career decision making?*

There is basket full of factors influence career decision making of high school students as per several studies like students' confidence in their academic abilities, ethnic identity, relationships with family, school factors, social economic status (Austin, 2010). Roach, (2010) added how the social environment for example role models of environment, parental support, teacher support, and peer support influence secondary students' career decision making (Scott & Ciani, 2008; Grygo, 2006). Identity issue is the most relevant one in the stage of adolescent that influence CDM (Holcomb-McCoy, 2005). Experience of success, verbal persuasion and psychological condition (lack of expectation, feeling of being unwanted etc) play major role in case of career choice (Bandura, 1997; Buckham, L., 1988). The educational qualification of parents and the family income affect career decision making self-efficacy levels (Gesinde, 2001; Ferry, 2006; Bolat & Odaci, 2017). In vietnam, respect for authority, a commitment to hard work and education comprising the cultural values of Vietnam may affect CDM (Patel et al., 2008). As well as low literacy level and lack of career information, self-efficacy, achievement motivation also influence high school students' career selecting decision (Guest, Lotze & Wallace, 2015; Kaur & Kumari, 2018). CDM is largely influenced by self-confidence, social support also (Okediji et al., 2008; You, 2013).

C. *How the career decision making efficacy can be cultivated?*

Keeping eyes on the need of the development of career decision making efficacy among higher secondary students, Government of several countries have introduced various programs. Similarly, researchers have suggested many ways for curriculum planners to redesign curriculum accordingly. Murry & Pujar (2017) gave importance of counsellors for assisting students in their career decision making processes. In spite of enhancing the counselling service, awareness programmes with respect helping students in career related decisions can be organized for the parents, teachers, guides, educational institutions and mentors (Monteiro, 2015; Das et al., 2020). Kaur (2017) emphasized on efficient arrangements of guidance and counselling programs in schools related to various career opportunities and career decision making. It is a matter of concern for teachers, parents and school administration considering the abilities and interest, guide students to take right career decision at right time (Meher & Kaur, 2015). Rani (2021) supported the counselling techniques, teacher's support and parental encouragement for the inculcation of strong CDM among high school students. Emphasis on organizing seminars, workshops, lectures from guest speakers for adolescents by school administrators and teachers and provide collaborative support and training on career guidance to parents by Professional school counsellors are the effective mechanisms (Kaur & Singh, 2018). Counsellors and teachers should design career interventions for secondary students (Wen et

al., 2019). Patel et al., (2008) joined something additional like career counsellors with their expertise in vocational psychology and multiculturalism are fit enough for guiding Vietnamese adolescents when they studied in context of role of acculturation, social support, socioeconomic status, and racism. In case of gifted learners, understanding of their level of career decision making is the vital thing then only proper career counselling programs could be systematically implemented for them (Abidin et al. 2019).

III. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Career decision making is considered as the strongest process for selection or matter of choice for students when selecting a particular career. This process helps to identify the related factors involved in it and provides an understanding of how these factors affect their career decision making and career choices. Young women reported higher level of career decision-making self-efficacy than young men and female learners are significantly more highly influenced than male in career decision making. These are the major findings of recent abroad studies by Abdinoor (2020), Olmos- Gómez et al., (2021), Chinyamurindi et al., (2021). It is supported by Sharma (2014) among Indian studies. Interesting matter is that also career indecisiveness scores of higher secondary girls were found slightly higher than the boys with respect to their career decision making by Das et al., (2020) from an Indian study. But Bolat & Odacı (2017), Patel et al., (2008), Aka (2020) among abroad studies opposed them by their findings as no significant relationship of gender with the level of career decision making self-efficacy, which is supported by Kaur & Kumari (2018), showed insignificant difference between career decision making of students with respect to gender.

Least studies in abroad and a few studies have been conducted in India on career decision making with respect to locality. Due to lack of sufficient number of studies on career decision making and about their possible related factors both in abroad and India, Students are still facing severe difficulties to decide a suitable career for them, that ultimately leads to career frustration and incompetency in job sector. It creates a big challenge for the individuals those who are already in the period of stress and strain. Therefore, it is depicted by the researcher that such kind of meta-analysis would provide opportunities to identify the research gaps for the further research and to highlight the suggestive measures of many researches for undertaking huge number of age and level specific career guidance programmes for the novice career planner.

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